

A life cycle assessment model to evaluate the environmental sustainability of lignin-based polyols

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ABSTRACT

Lignin-based polyols are expected to provide significant environmental benefits by offering new synthetic routes to various types of bio-resins for coating applications. Currently, no models evaluating lignin-based polyols are available in the literature, therefore, the present study introduces a new model to assess environmental impacts associated with the synthesis of lignin-based polyols and to evaluate their potential environmental advantages in bio-product manufacturing. The model follows the life cycle assessment methodology and is based on lignin-based polyols production at a pilot scale, beginning with kraft lignin extraction, followed by solvent fractionation. The results indicate that, compared to their petrochemical counterparts, lignin-based polyols demonstrate superior environmental performance under specific conditions, such as the use of bio-based solvents and an appropriate energy mix. Tetrahydrofuran and electricity consumption emerge as the primary hotspots contributing to environmental impact categories such as climate change, fossil resource use, and water use—identified as the main contributors to the overall environmental impact of lignin-based polyol production. An uncertainty analysis was conducted using Monte Carlo simulation. Based on the findings, producers can consider lignin-based polyols as a promising raw material if they replace tetrahydrofuran with its bio-based counterpart and adopt a renewable energy mix for production. This model can be easily extended by researchers and/or practitioners to further evaluate the environmental impacts of bio-products derived from lignin-based polyols. Moreover, the results of this study can guide policymakers in shaping bio-product policies, as lignin-based polyols show promise as a more sustainable chemical alternative.

1. Introduction

Lignin is the most prevalent and abundant heteropolymer in nature, accounting for approximately 15–32 % of the total biomass (Roy et al., 2022). In recent decades, lignin has demonstrated significant potential for various applications, including biofuels production and more recently, bio-based chemicals such as plastic polymers, bitumen in asphalts, urea-formaldehyde in adhesives, polyol in polyisocyanurate foams or polyacrylonitrile in carbon fibers (Moretti et al., 2021). While converting lignin into valuable chemical intermediates poses challenges,

it holds significant potential to replace petrochemical alternatives over time. Lignin is primarily a byproduct of the pulping industry (Khan et al., 2019; Ragauskas et al., 2014). During chemical pulping, lignin is generally dissolved in cooking liquor when wood or straw is digested to produce cellulose-rich pulp fibers (CTCN, 2023). In the kraft process, lignin in black liquor is typically burned in a recovery boiler to generate energy for mill operations (Bernier et al., 2013). However, in line with circular economy principles, kraft lignin can also be recovered through acid precipitation and repurposed in a variety of chemical applications (Susilo and Chaniago, 2020).

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It is crucial to assess whether the recovery and utilization of lignin have environmental impacts that justify its use as a promising raw material compared to its petrochemical alternatives. Bernier et al. (2013) and Culbertson et al. (2016) conducted a life cycle assessment (LCA) to assess the environmental impacts of recovering lignin from the kraft pulping process. Bernier et al. (2013) concluded that kraft lignin is generally a more environmentally favorable option compared to synthetic organic compounds of similar molecular structures, particularly in polymer applications. Culbertson et al. (2016) supported these findings, confirming that kraft lignin reduces environmental impact. However, previous studies have shown that the environmental benefits of lignin-based products compared to petrochemical counterparts highly depend on various factors, such as the lignin type and production processes (Montazeri and Eckelman, 2016).

One promising application of kraft lignin is its conversion into polyols. Polyols, which contain multiple alcoholic hydroxyl groups, are essential components of polyurethanes used in industries like construction, automotive, and refrigeration (Markets and Markets, 2023). Over the past decades, the environmental impacts of polyol synthesis from different feedstocks have been extensively studied. For instance, Von der Assen and Bardow (2014) conducted an LCA for CO₂-based polyether carbonate polyols produced at an industrial pilot plant, showing that environmental impact decreases as CO₂ content increases. Fridrihsone et al. (2020) performed a cradle-to-gate LCA at the pilot scale, demonstrating that bio-based polyols outperform petrochemical polyols (PPO) in 8 out of the 18 ReCiPe midpoint impact categories. Among various applications, the utilization of bio-based polyols for polyurethane, alkyd, or epoxy resins has received particular attention (Suzuki et al., 2016; Gondaliya and Nejad, 2021; Duval et al., 2022), but almost no attention has been given to life cycle assessments applied to lignin-based polyols (LPO).

To our knowledge, only two studies have focused on applying the LCA methodology to LPO. The first of these studies by Manzardo et al. (2019) investigated polyurethane foams using LPO derived from azelaic acid as a potential raw material. However, the focus of Manzardo et al. (2019) was to assess different raw materials for polyurethane foams, resulting in a highly simplified environmental model of LPO. Their model did not compare LPO with PPO, nor did it provide industrial recommendations on how LPO could emerge as a viable, environmentally sustainable candidate for bio-product manufacturing. The absence of a detailed environmental model for LPO may result in its exclusion as a candidate for sustainable bio-polyol production due to the lack of environmental assessment data and industry-specific recommendations for ensuring environmental sustainability. The second study, conducted by Cavalaglio et al. (2023) presents a comprehensive LCA of LPO production through organosolv fractionation of cardoon stalks and subsequent lignin liquefaction. This study found that all stages of the production chain significantly influenced overall environmental impacts. Although this paper provides a comprehensive LCA, it focuses on organosolv LPO. Even though the aforementioned papers present the application of the LCA methodology to LPO, no paper was found that focuses on kraft LPO. Moreover, one of these studies did not focus on LPO itself but rather on the bio-product derived from LPO, i.e., polyurethane foams (Manzardo et al., 2019). Consequently, this study presents a greatly simplified environmental model of LPO. Lastly, none of the reviewed studies compares LPO and PPO or provides industrial recommendations on how LPO could emerge as a viable, environmentally sustainable candidate for bio-product manufacturing.

To address these gaps, this paper introduces a new environmental assessment model based on the LCA methodology of LPO derived from kraft lignin, along with industry guidelines on how to ensure the environmental sustainability of LPO as a raw material for numerous bio-products. The model provides a comprehensive evaluation of LPO, enabling future assessments of bio-based products that utilize LPO as raw material to incorporate the present model into their analyses. Additionally, this study presents a direct comparison between LPO and

PPO to assess whether LPO is a sustainable alternative to PPO. The proposed model and the industrial recommendations provided in this study are intended to assist: i) practitioners in determining LPO's sustainability for different products; ii) researchers and practitioners incorporating LPO into LCA models for bioproducts; and iii) researchers and practitioners aiming to further improve LPO production by reducing environmental impacts through technological advancements.

This study is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the methods and proposed model, Section 3 discusses the results and recommendations, and Section 4 provides the conclusions of the manuscript.

2. Methods

A comparative attributional LCA was developed considering the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) guidelines for LCA (ISO, 2006a, 2006b). The LCA stages proposed in ISO are: i) goal and scope definition ii) life cycle inventory iii) life cycle impact assessment, and iv) interpretation.

2.1. Goal and scope definition

2.1.1. Goal

The key purpose of this study is twofold. First, to identify the main hotspots in the production of LPO as a diagnosis and propose alternatives for future environmental improvements. Second, to compare the potential environmental impacts caused by the synthesis of LPO, with those of PPO.

2.1.2. Scope

Defining the scope involves establishing the boundaries and the declared unit, presenting the allocation methods, and stating the system and main assumptions. The physical boundary chosen in this study is cradle-to-gate, which considers a life cycle from the resource extraction (cradle) until the factory gate. The use phase and end-of-life of the products were excluded, as lignin-based and conventional polyols have similar properties, resulting in final products with the same function and durability (e.g., polyurethane dispersion (PUD) and alkyd resins for coatings applications). This means that the production of final products, the distribution, the use, and the disposal phases will present the same environmental impacts and therefore they will not contribute to the comparison of the two sources of polyols. Moreover, the purpose of the study is to obtain results for polyols, so subsequent applications fall outside its scope. The physical boundary considered in the polyol production system is depicted in Figs. 1 through 3 distinct steps.

2.1.3. Declared unit

The declared unit stipulated in terms of the final product (considered in the physical boundary) is the most used in LCA studies dealing with the production of commodity chemicals, energy being second. In this work, the following declared unit was chosen: 1 kg of polyol (lignin or petroleum-based) to produce PUD and alkyd resins for coatings applications.

2.1.4. Allocation system

For this study, various allocation systems were considered, starting with the kraft lignin. The latter is the product of a multi-output process, primarily aimed at producing pulp for the paper industry (Mathew et al., 2018). Therefore, an economic allocation was applied to the production of kraft lignin, using the price of 535€ per ton (Moretti et al., 2021), which corresponds to an allocation factor of 7.3%, based on the prices of the other outputs. Three additional inputs—sulfuric acid, liquid carbon dioxide, and natural gas—were fully allocated to lignin production, along with their respective environmental impacts. For the second step of the value chain, which involves lignin fractionation, a mass allocation was employed, as two products were obtained at the end of this process: the soluble and the insoluble lignin fractions. These fractions are

Fig. 1. System boundaries of polyols production.

Fig. 2. Single score comparison between lignin-based polyols and petroleum-based polyols.

Fig. 3. Pareto analysis for lignin-based polyols.

subsequently valorized into polyols (Step 3) and dispersants (e.g., for dispersing special carbon black pigments) (Fearon et al., 2021; Kalliola et al., 2022), respectively. An allocation factor of 30 % was assigned to the soluble lignin fraction based on the mass of the products.

2.2. Life cycle inventory

Data inventories were either modeled or collected, encompassing material resources, energy and water usage, emissions, and waste. Both primary and secondary data were utilized in the inventory model. Primary data are experimentally obtained at the laboratory or semi-industrial scale, while secondary data consist of generic or average information sourced from databases or literature. The proposed model for LPO is aligned with the operations described in Fig. 1.

2.2.1. Model description for LPO

2.2.1.1. Step 1: Lignin production. The industrial softwood kraft lignin raw material was provided by Stora-Enso. For the production of the polyols, the aqueous ethanol soluble fraction of this softwood kraft lignin was utilized. Due to the lack of primary data, the data from Culbertson et al. (2016), as cited in Moretti et al. (2021), was used as the main data source. In this study, dry kraft lignin production was modeled starting from the kraft process where wood is converted into pulp. Typically, the lignin by-product in black liquor is burnt for energy, but a portion of it can be extracted and recovered through an acid precipitation process. The initial step of this process involves lignin precipitation using carbon dioxide (CO₂). Following this, the precipitation and washing stages are conducted with sulfuric acid to remove mineral impurities, primarily sodium. Finally, dewatering and drying steps yield the end-product—dry kraft lignin. All process flows were modeled by adapting Moretti et al. (2021) to fit the scope of this model. The production of kraft lignin takes place in Finland, so secondary data retrieved from the literature was adjusted to reflect the production conditions in Finland. This includes using a Finnish-specific electricity mix for the manufacturing phase. Detailed data on the process can be found in Table 1.

Table 1

Life cycle inventory data for kraft lignin production, output: 1 ton of kraft lignin.

Flow	Unit	Amount	Comments/data source
Inputs			
Sulfuric acid for lignin extraction	ton	7.00×10^{-2}	Culbertson et al., 2016
Natural gas for lignin extraction	MJ	1.03×10^3	Culbertson et al., 2016
Liquid carbon dioxide for lignin extraction (CO ₂)	ton	2.80×10^{-1}	Culbertson et al., 2016
Sodium hydroxide	ton	1.00×10^{-1}	Culbertson et al., 2016
Lime	ton	4.10×10^{-1}	Culbertson et al., 2016
Natural gas	MJ	2.10×10^4	Culbertson et al., 2016
Softwood	m ³	4.99×10^1	Culbertson et al., 2016
Combustion of hog fuel	MJ	1.52×10^5	Culbertson et al., 2016
Outputs			
Kraft lignin	ton	1.00	Culbertson et al., 2016
Waste to landfill	ton	1.07	Culbertson et al., 2016
Sulfur dioxide direct emissions	kg	2.70×10^{-1}	Culbertson et al., 2016
Fossil carbon dioxide direct emissions	kg	1.40×10^3	Culbertson et al., 2016

2.2.1.2. Step 2: Lignin fractionation. Lignin fractionation using membranes or solvent systems is commonly employed to separate lignin into different components with more uniform physicochemical properties (Gigli and Crestini, 2020). The primary approach in solvent fractionation of lignin involves solubilizing a portion of the lignin in a suitable solvent system and filtering out the insoluble fraction. The soluble fraction is then recovered either by solvent evaporation or by precipitation using an anti-solvent, such as water. For example, when using aqueous ethanol or acetone, the soluble lignin fraction exhibits a lower molar mass, a higher amount of phenolic or carboxylic acid groups, and a lower glass transition temperature than the insoluble lignin fraction (Domínguez-Robles et al., 2018; Jääskeläinen et al., 2017). Although various types of lignin and solvent fractionation techniques have been explored, most have been limited to laboratory-scale tests and primarily focused on characterizing lignin properties or testing the performance of the most promising lignin fractions.

A pilot scale solvent fractionation of kraft lignin was performed by the Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT). Based on the best results from laboratory experiments, lignin fractionation was performed at a 65:35 volume ratio of ethanol to water. For safety reasons, the pilot-scale solvent fractionation was carried out using ATEX-certified equipment. The reactor setup used was a Drais TurbuDry TD 250 E. Lignin was added to aqueous ethanol at 10.1 wt% concentration, and the slurry was mixed at 25 °C for two hours in the 250 L reactor. After the mixing process, the suspension of lignin in solvent was filtered after the mixing time using industrial filter fabric. The insoluble fraction was rejected by the fabric while the soluble fraction passed through the filter. The insoluble fraction was washed with an aqueous ethanol mixture, dried, and weighed. The soluble fraction was concentrated by evaporating the solvent and then freeze-dried and weighed. The yield of the soluble lignin fraction was 30 % of the initial kraft lignin (Ghosh et al., 2024). The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of the fractionation step is presented in Table 2.

2.2.1.3. Step 3: Polyol production. The LPO synthesis was initially performed at a laboratory scale by TECNALIA and then upscaled by AEP Polymers. Following the most effective TECNALIA protocol, the LPO synthesis took place in a three-necked 5 L glass-jacketed reactor at room temperature and atmospheric pressure, equipped with a mechanical stirrer. Pre-dried lignin (at 50 °C in a drying oven) was added to the reactor and blended with tetrahydrofuran (THF) under moderate stirring. For the THF, it was anticipated that solvent recycling would be feasible at an industrial scale. According to the technical information sheet on THF recovery, overall THF recovery rates range from 85 to 97

Table 2

Life cycle inventory data for the manufacturing of lignin fractions, output: 1 kg of aqueous ethanol soluble lignin fraction.

Flow	Unit	Amount	Comments/data source
Inputs			
Kraft lignin	kg	3.54	Provided by VTT
Ethanol	kg	5.50×10^{-1}	Provided by VTT
Water	kg	1.24×10^1	Provided by VTT
Outputs			
Fractionated lignin	kg	1.00	Provided by VTT
Insoluble lignin	kg	2.44	Provided by VTT Valorized into dispersant for special carbon black in coatings
Ethanol (for reuse)	kg	1.76×10^1	Provided by VTT
Ethanol (lost)	kg	5.50×10^{-1}	Provided by VTT: Typically min 95 % should be recycled. Small part of EtOH could be lost in the product, wastewater, leak in recovery/evaporation
Water	m ³	1.24×10^1	Provided by VTT

%). In this specific case, based on partner feedback, it was predicted that the recovery would be at the higher end of the range, so a 95 % recovery rate of the solvent was assumed for modeling purposes. Once the reaction mixture became homogeneous, boron trifluoride etherate catalyst was added while stirring. Subsequently, butylene oxide was continuously added at a rate of 73 mL of oxirane per lignin hydroxyl group per hour. After the oxirane addition was completed, the mixture was stirred for an additional hour to ensure full conversion. The catalyst was then neutralized by cooling it down with an excess of *N,N*-dimethylethylamine (1.66 equivalents referred to the catalyst), and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure for 2 h at 60 °C, yielding the desired LPO. Polyol production occurs in Italy, and the primary data provided by AEP Polymers aligns with the Italian context. The following proxies were used, with approval from AEP Polymers, the partner responsible for the synthesis:

- *N,N*-dimethylethylamine: Triethyl amine
- Butylene oxide: Propylene oxide

The LCI of the LPO synthesis step is detailed in Table 3.

2.2.2. Model description for PPO

The comparison was made with an average petroleum-based polyol, for which a mix of European production countries was considered. The polyol production data is based on information from 2023, ensuring that the reference year for other life cycle data is as close as possible to 2023. Data was retrieved from the Eco-profiles of the European plastics industry (Plastics Europe). The following values were excluded from the inventory: the amount of recyclable wastes, consumption of air / N₂ / O₂, unspecified chlorofluorocarbon (CFC) and hydrochlorofluorocarbon (HCFC), unspecified metal emission to water and air, mercaptan emission to air, and dioxin emissions to water. Additionally, the quantity of “sulfur (bonded)” is assumed to be included in the total quantity of raw oil.

Table 3

Life cycle inventory data for lignin-based polyol synthesis, declared unit: 1 kg of polyol.

Flow	Unit	Amount/ Declared Unit	Comments/data source
Inputs			
Fractionated lignin	kg	3.00×10^{-1}	Life Cycle Assessment of lignin extraction in a softwood kraft pulp mill, published by Culbertson et al. (2016) and primary data provided by VTT
Butylene oxide	kg	1.50×10^{-1}	Provided by AEP Polymers
Tetrahydrofuran	kg	5.93×10^{-1}	AEP (Initial quantity 1.7 kg, 0.535 kg consumed during the reaction. Remanning quantity of THF can be reused 10 times. Net consumption of 0.6515 (0.535 + 0.1165))
Boron trifluoride etherate	kg	2.40×10^{-2}	Provided by AEP Polymers
<i>N,N</i> -dimethylethylamine	kg	2.10×10^{-2}	Provided by AEP Polymers
Electricity	kWh	4.40	Provided by AEP Polymers
Outputs			
Lignin-based polyol	kg	1.00	Provided by AEP Polymers
Tetrahydrofuran	kg	5.83×10^{-2}	Provided by AEP Polymers
Traces of remaining volatile compounds	kg	3.00×10^{-2}	Provided by AEP Polymers Neglected

2.2.3. General modeling assumptions

- The following steps were not included in the scope of this LCA:
- **Machinery manufacturing:** the impacts associated with machinery manufacturing such as the dryer, stirrer, reactor, etc., are not considered. Indeed, given the lifespan of such technologies (between 10 and 20 years depending on the machine), their impact on the system was excluded. This decision was made because these technologies are widely used for various products, and the environmental impact allocated to each product would be minimal, leading to a negligible contribution to the overall impact.
- **Transportation of raw materials and intermediate products:** Due to the project's geographical spread, raw materials and intermediate products often travel long distances and pass through several transit points before reaching the factory. This transportation stage, along with the associated emissions, must be defined carefully. Therefore, the LCA only considers the materials once they arrive at the production site. At this stage of technological development, no meaningful logistics data was available for modeling transportation. However, when “market for” references were available for specific flows, transportation was included using average values.
- **Marketing and packaging:** This aspect of the value chain was excluded from the assessment, as the technology is still at an early stage, making it difficult to quantify the impacts before full-scale commercialization. However, these factors will be considered for future recommendations.
- **Services and maintenance operations:** The environmental impacts associated with administrative tasks, quality control, logistics, management, marketing, etc., are also excluded. These services have indirect environmental impacts from energy consumption (e.g., lighting, heating, and water usage in buildings). Similarly, maintenance operations on both the factory and machinery—often involving transportation, energy, and material consumption (such as oils and paints)—are not included at this stage. Such impacts could be factored in once the process reaches an industrial scale.

2.2.4. Data quality assessment

Data quality was evaluated in accordance with ISO (2006a, 2006b) based on several criteria: representativeness (including technological, completeness, and geographical time-related aspects), methodological consistency, and appropriateness. The results of the evaluation indicate that the data quality can be classified as “good” to “very good” for the primary data and “fair” to “good” for secondary data. The data quality assessment was conducted according to the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) category rules, and a snapshot of the data quality for the main steps in polyol synthesis can be found in Table 4.

2.3. Life cycle impact assessment

The impact assessment method used was the PEF, as recommended by the European Commission (Commission Recommendations 2013/179/EU). This method encompasses the following impact categories: acidification potential (AP), climate change (CC), freshwater ecotoxicity (FET), freshwater eutrophication (FE), human toxicity cancer (HT_c), human toxicity non-cancer (HT_{nc}), ionizing radiation (IR), land use (LU), marine eutrophication (ME), ozone depletion (OD), particulate matter (PM), photochemical ozone formation (POF), resource use, fossil (RU_f), resource use, minerals and metals (RU_m), terrestrial eutrophication (TE), and water use (WU).

2.4. Interpretation

This final step encompasses the presentation and interpretation of the obtained results in a concise manner.

In this manuscript, the results were analyzed as follows:

Table 4
Data quality assessment for the main production steps.

Production step	Geographical representativeness	Technical representativeness	Time representativeness
<i>Kraft lignin production</i>	<i>Good, Data adapted to the Finnish context and extrapolated from European average</i>	<i>Good, the technological aspects of the production are captured</i>	<i>Good</i>
<i>Lignin fractionation</i>	<i>Very good (primary data)</i>	<i>Very good (primary data)</i>	<i>Very good (primary data)</i>
<i>Polyols synthesis</i>	<i>Very good (primary data)</i>	<i>Very good (primary data)</i>	<i>Very good (primary data)</i>

- **Overall environmental impact** (single score and characterized values) – A comparison between the environmental impact of the LPO and PPO in terms of both single score and characterized values.
- **Critical environmental impacts** – Identification of the impact categories that generate the most significant environmental impact related to the LPO synthesis. To identify these categories, a Pareto analysis was employed (Carvalho et al., 2014). A Pareto analysis is a statistical procedure that aims to identify the impact categories that make the greatest contribution to the single score. Since the impact categories have different measurement units, Pareto analysis can be applied only after the characterized results are normalized and weighted.
- **Hotspots** – Identification of the life cycle processes that contribute most significantly to the critical environmental impacts identified earlier.
- **Potential alternatives** – Proposal of alternatives to reduce the environmental impact of the LPO synthesis based on the previous diagnosis. A comparison of the environmental impact of these alternatives with the current LPO synthesis process and PPO will be assessed through a sensitivity analysis. The results of the sensitivity analysis are presented in Section 4.
- **Uncertainty analysis** – Numerous parameters (i.e., characterization, inventory, weighting factors, and normalization) are applied when performing an LCA. The uncertainty associated with these parameters introduces uncertainty in the results of an LCA (Huijbregts, 1998). For this reason, it is crucial to consider parameter uncertainty when conducting an LCA. In this study, the work developed by Santos et al. (2023) was utilized to analyze the impacts of parameter uncertainty in comparing the environmental impact of the proposed alternatives with the environmental impact of the current LPO synthesis process and PPO. The methodology presented by Santos et al. (2023) employs Monte Carlo simulation. Probability distributions must be assigned to parameters with uncertainty when conducting this type of simulation. Following the study by Santos et al. (2023), a lognormal distribution was assigned to the uncertain data used to model the systems in this study (e.g., PPO). For each data point used, the two parameters that characterized this distribution, namely the geometric mean and the geometric standard deviation (Muller et al., 2016), were defined. The geometric mean corresponds to the deterministic value used to determine the inventory in the deterministic LCA, while the geometric standard deviation is determined by considering the basic uncertainty factor and additional uncertainty information attributed to each data point (Table S5 available in Supplementary Information file). A uniform distribution was attributed to each characterization factor and each normalization factor (Santos et al., 2023). This distribution is characterized by two parameters, namely the minimum and the maximum of the distribution (Muller et al., 2016) (Table S6 and Table S7 available in Supplementary Information file). After assigning the probability distributions, the uncertain parameters were sampled from these distributions. Following the approach by Santos et al. (2023), the Latin Hypercube sampling was selected and a total of 10,000 iterations were defined as the stopping criteria for the simulation. The Monte Carlo simulation was performed using the @Risk software (Palisade Corporation, 2016). The inputs of the

simulation are the inventory, characterization factors, and normalization factors sampled at random. In each iteration, a total of 126,624 inputs were generated. The outputs of this model were defined according to the results analyzed in the deterministic LCA and include the stochastic characterized results of the most critical impact categories and the stochastic single scores. The stochastic results obtained were analyzed using statistical hypothesis tests (Santos et al., 2023). In a statistical hypothesis test, the null hypothesis (H_0) proposed is rejected if the probability value (p -value) calculated is lower or equal to a given significance level (α) (Graybill et al., 1998). In this study, these tests were conducted in Python (Python Software Foundation, 2022) and a 0.05 significance level was defined since it is the most chosen (Ross, 2017). Three assumptions must be confirmed to determine the most appropriate statistical hypothesis test (Graybill et al., 1998):

- Independence of observations: The stochastic results obtained are independent because the results gathered for each system analyzed (e.g., PPO) do not affect the results obtained for the other systems (e.g., the current LPO synthesis process);
- Normality of data: In sufficiently large sample datasets, verifying this assumption is unnecessary. Previous simulation studies suggest that “sufficiently large” typically means fewer than 100 data points (Lumley et al., 2002). Given that 10,000 iterations were performed, the sets of stochastic results are deemed sufficiently large, and this assumption was not verified;
- Homogeneity of variance: The Levene's test (Lim and Loh, 1996) was used to test the null hypothesis of equal variances among the stochastic results. In this test, a probability value of 0.05 or lower indicates statistical evidence of unequal variances, prompting the use of a Student's t -test for pairwise comparison of the stochastic results. Conversely, a p -value above 0.05 indicates statistical evidence of equal variances, in which case a Welch's t -test was used for pairwise comparisons. Subsection 3.6 presents the results of the uncertainty analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Overall environmental impact

The LPO has been compared with the PPO described in section 2.2.2. The single score was selected as the initial comparison to determine if LPO can be a more environmentally sustainable choice to replace PPO. Results from Fig. 2 indicate that LPO is slightly more advantageous than PPO; however, there is a need to identify the impact categories that contribute most significantly (through Pareto analysis) and to pinpoint the hotspots within each category. This understanding will provide recommendations to the industry regarding the production conditions necessary to establish LPO as a more environmentally friendly alternative (see Sections 3.2 and 3.3). As a preliminary observation, Fig. 2 shows that CC, RU_f and WU have a higher contribution to LPO production impacts. This gap is explained in Section 3.3.

When we compare the mid-point impact categories of LPO and PPO (Table 5), it can be stated that LPO exhibits lower impacts in five out of sixteen impact categories, namely PM, HT_{nc} , FE, ME, FET. Therefore, it is essential to identify the most impactful categories, which are outlined

Table 5
Mid-point impacts comparison with numerical values between lignin-based polyols and petroleum-based polyols (per declared unit).

	Unit	Lignin-based polyol	Petroleum-based polyol
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	5.79	4.03
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	4.0×10^{-7}	1.83×10^{-9}
Ionizing radiation	kBq U-235 eq	0.28	1.19×10^{-3}
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	0.019	0.012
Particulate matter	disease inc.	2.18×10^{-7}	6.92×10^{-7}
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	1.06×10^{-7}	1.36×10^{-7}
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	2.17×10^{-9}	4.11×10^{-10}
Acidification	mol H ⁺ eq	0.022	0.017
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	2.20×10^{-4}	4.33×10^{-4}
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	3.7×10^{-3}	4.25×10^{-3}
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	0.041	0.035
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	70.84	377.85
Land use	Pt	82.40	0.099
Water use	m ³ depriv.	9.83	5.41
Resource use, fossils	MJ	104.41	82.23
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	3.92×10^{-5}	6.69×10^{-7}

in the section 3.2 through a Pareto analysis. This aims to pinpoint the process hotspots discussed in Section 3.3, enabling the provision of recommendations that can further improve the environmental impact of LPO. This preliminary part of the study facilitates a diagnostic assessment and proposes actions to reduce the impacts of LPO in Section 3.4.

3.2. Critical environmental impacts

As mentioned in the previous section, the gap between the single

Fig. 4. Impact distribution for lignin-based polyols.

scores of the two polyols was not substantial; therefore, a Pareto analysis was performed to identify the most contributing impact categories and to understand how LPO can be produced more sustainably. The Pareto analysis represented in Fig. 3 identifies the most significant environmental categories for LPO as CC, RU_f, and WU. For the other impact categories, it can be observed that their relative contribution are below 10 %.

3.3. Hotspots

After identifying the impact categories with the highest contribution, an additional analysis was conducted to determine the most impactful processes within each critical impact category for the LPO. Fig. 4 illustrates the hotspots in the value chain (most impactful processes), for each impact category. For the three most significant categories identified (CC, RU_f and WU), Fig. 4 shows that THF is the primary contributor, accounting for 47.87 %, 53.14 % and 80.62 % of the total impact, respectively. The electricity generated from the Italian energy mix for the LPO synthesis also contributes significantly, representing 33.26 %, 28.11 % and 12.09 % for CC, RU_f and WU, respectively. Finally, propylene oxide also has a noteworthy impact, accounting for 9.96 % and 12.41 % of the total impact for CC and RU_f, respectively. In summary, it can be said that THF production is among the most impactful processes for ten out of sixteen impact categories, followed closely by electricity consumption during the process.

3.3.1. The solvent THF

From Fig. 4, the solvent THF used for the LPO production is a highly sensitive parameter in the analysis. This solvent serves both as a solvent and a reagent during the synthesis, imparting specific properties to the LPO. Fig. 5 provides a clear visual indication that the significant impact of THF is primarily attributed to the Butane-1,4-diol (1,4-BDO), which is an organic compound dehydrated to produce the solvent.

According to Moutousidi and Kookos (2021), a new bio-based method for synthesizing 1,4-BDO and THF includes the bioconversion

**Legend: Europe (RER)
Global (GLO)
Italy (IT)**

Fig. 5. Main contributions to the environmental impacts given the declared unit.

of sugars. In their study, the authors further analyzed the environmental performance of manufacturing biobased chemicals like 1,4-BDO considering various sources of fermentable sugars, such as sugarcane, as feedstock in the proposed alternatives through a sensitivity analysis.

3.3.2. The electricity consumption

As shown in Fig. 4, electricity consumption was identified as a significant contributor to the overall potential impact, particularly for CC, RU_f and WU. Consequently, alternative European electricity mixes were evaluated against the current electricity use from the Italian grid, where the original process occurs, as illustrated in Fig. 6. In the case of CC, utilizing electricity mixes from Switzerland (which emphasizes renewable energy), Sweden, and France significantly reduces the overall impact of the LPO synthesis. For RU, only the Swiss renewable energy mix notably decreased the impact of the LPO. For the remaining impact categories, however, the results showed no significant changes.

For the three most impactful categories identified earlier, the total values were recalculated and expressed as percentage differences from the original scenario. Table 6 displays the exact fluctuations for these categories based on the chosen energy mix. The various scenarios demonstrate that the environmental impact can either decrease or increase depending on the electricity production method included in the value chain. Utilizing the energy mix from Switzerland, which emphasizes renewable energy, results in the most significant percentage reduction compared to the baseline scenario: -32% for CC, -10% for WU and -28% for RU_f . These reductions are attributed to the minimal reliance on fossil fuels in this mix. Conversely, adopting an energy mix with a high proportion of fossil resources, such as that of Germany, results in a greater environmental impact than the baseline scenario for the LPO.

3.4. Potential alternatives

Based on the previous diagnosis, which identified different hotspots in the current value chain, two alternative scenarios aiming to reduce the total environmental impact were proposed. Scenario S1 serves as the reference scenario, Scenario S2 is a realistic improvement scenario, and Scenario S3 represents the best-performing scenario. More details are provided below:

Table 6

Detail of the sensitivity analysis performed in Fig. 6 (Italy is taken as a reference).

Lignin-based polyol production country	Climate change	Water use	Resource use, fossil
France	-26%	-10%	$+31\%$
Spain	-9%	-3%	$+8\%$
Sweden	-30%	-8%	$+2\%$
Germany	$+4\%$	-11%	$+3\%$
Switzerland (renewable energy products)	-32%	-10%	-28%

- **Scenario 1 (reference):** This scenario utilizes the LCI modeled in this article (available in Section 2.2.1. Model description for LPO).
- **Scenario 2 (realistic):** In this scenario, the THF is replaced by bio-based THF (bio-based 1,4-BDO was modeled in SimaPro using the Life Cycle Inventory of the authors Moutousidi and Kookos (2021) and replaced in the THF inventory of the database Ecoinvent to obtain the bio-based THF). The corresponding inventory can be found in Table S4 in the Supplementary Information file.
- **Scenario 3 (best-performing):** This scenario combines the use of bio-based THF with a renewable energy mix.

These three scenarios have been compared against PPO for the impact categories CC, RU_f , WU, and single score, as illustrated in the following figures.

For the CC impact category (Fig. 7), it is evident that the realistic scenario exhibits better environmental performance than its fossil counterpart. The best-performing scenario demonstrates an emission level of $1.91\text{ kg CO}_2\text{ eq}$, which represents a reduction of over 50% compared to the PPO. Overall, the replacement of THF with its bio-based version, coupled with the use of a renewable energy mix, results in a 67% reduction in the original result of the reference scenario (decreasing from 5.79 to $1.91\text{ kg CO}_2\text{ eq}$).

For the RU_f impact category (Fig. 8), transitioning from THF to bio-based THF in the realistic scenario results in a significant reduction in total impact, decreasing from 104.41 MJ to 58.83 MJ —a reduction of nearly 44% . In the best-performing scenario, where a renewable energy mix is utilized, the fossil resource use is further minimized, bringing the

Fig. 6. Analysis of the electricity mix on the impacts of the manufacturing of 1 kg of lignin-based polyols. Italy is taken as a reference.

Fig. 7. Scenarios comparison for climate change – 1 kg of polyol.

Fig. 8. Scenarios comparison for resource use, fossils – 1 kg of polyol.

value down to 29.52 MJ. Compared to the PPO, the realistic and best-performing scenarios demonstrate reductions of 29 % and 64 %, respectively.

For the WU impact category (Fig. 9), the adoption of the bio-based version of THF leads to a substantial decrease in water consumption in the realistic scenario, which achieves an impact comparable to the best-performing scenario that utilizes a renewable energy mix. In the reference scenario, 9.83 m³ world eq was required to produce 1 kg of LPO. By switching to bio-based THF and implementing a renewable energy mix, this figure is reduced to 2.77 m³ world eq and 1.70 m³ world eq for the realistic and best-performing scenarios, respectively. In contrast, the PPO requires 5.42 m³ world eq, indicating a 37 % reduction in the LPO-realistic scenario compared to its petroleum-based counterpart.

Finally, for the single score (Fig. 10), the realistic scenario achieved a score of 432.91 μPt compared to 556.90 μPt for the current model. Substituting THF with its bio-based version results in a reduction in the three most significant impact categories identified earlier: CC, WU, and RU. In the best-performing scenario, where the Italian energy mix is replaced with a renewable energy mix, the score further decreases to 314.37 μPt. Compared to the PPO, the realistic scenario shows a 27 % reduction, which is accomplished by modifying just one parameter in the model: the use of bio-based THF.

3.5. Uncertainty analysis

Table 7 presents the probability values from the Levene's tests. As

Fig. 9. Scenarios comparison for water use – 1 kg of polyol.

Fig. 10. Scenario comparison-Single score.

previously mentioned in the Methodology, Levene's test (Lim and Loh, 1996) was used to test the null hypothesis of equal variances among the stochastic results (e.g., $H_0 : \sigma_{CC_PPO}^2 = \sigma_{CC_LPO_Actual}^2$). A p -value of 0.05 or lower indicates statistical evidence of unequal variances. For instance, as shown in Table 7, there is statistical evidence of homogeneity of variance between the PPO and LPO – Realistic Scenario stochastic CC results. Hence, a Student's t -test was used for the pairwise comparison between these results. On the other hand, the stochastic water use (WU) results demonstrate evidence of unequal variances between the two systems, leading to the use of a Welch's t -test for comparing those results. Table 8 presents the probability value obtained for the Student's/

Welch's t -tests used for pairwise comparisons.

According to Table 8, it can be concluded that the impact results for PPO and the realistic LPO scenario are statistically equivalent for the CC impact category. On the other hand, PPO was discovered to have significantly different impact results as the baseline and best-performing LPO scenarios for CC (Table 8). In this instance, a comparison between the means of the systems' stochastic results was performed to identify the more environmentally favorable system. The means presented in Table 8 indicate that the baseline LPO scenario has a higher impact on CC than PPO, even when considering uncertainty. This finding aligns with the result obtained from the deterministic LCA (Fig. 7). Moreover, looking

Table 7
Probability value of the Levene's tests.

		Climate change			Resource use, fossils			Water use			Single score			
		PPO	LPO Reference scenario	LPO Realistic scenario	LPO Best scenario	PPO	LPO Reference scenario	LPO Realistic scenario	LPO Best scenario	PPO	LPO Reference scenario	LPO Realistic scenario	LPO Best scenario	
Climate change	PPO	-	1.22E-03	2.29E-01	1.27E-01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	4.50E-01	4.45E-07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	2.21E-02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Resource use, fossils	PPO	-	-	-	-	3.13E-01	5.85E-03	9.55E-10	-	-	-	-	-	
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	-	-	-	1.38E-16	3.51E-55	-	-	-	-	-	
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.66E-16	-	-	-	-	-	
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Water use	PPO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.09E-258	-	-	
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.81E-01	5.02E-59	-	-	
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.52E-66	-	-	
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Single score	PPO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.05E-232	0.00E+00	1.57E-119
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.49E-01	2.16E-35
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.23E-53
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Legend: Petroleum-based polyol (PPO), Lignin-based polyols (LPO)
 p-value > 0.05 Indicates a statistical evidence of homogeneity of variance. A Student's t-test is the most appropriate choice to conduct the pairwise comparison.
 p-value ≤ 0.05 Indicates a statistical evidence of no homogeneity of variance. A Welch's t-test is the most appropriate choice to conduct the pairwise comparison.

Table 8
Probability value of the Student's/Welch's t-tests.

		Climate change			Resource use, fossils			Water use			Single score						
		PPO	LPO Reference scenario	LPO Realistic scenario	LPO Best scenario	PPO	LPO Reference scenario	LPO Realistic scenario	LPO Best scenario	PPO	LPO Reference scenario	LPO Realistic scenario	LPO Best scenario				
Climate change	PPO	-	7.63E-19	7.13E-01	1.30E-20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	9.64E-10	2.04E-88	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	2.90E-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
Resource use, fossils	PPO	-	-	-	-	1.04E-03	1.41E-10	2.26E-36	-	-	-	-	-				
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	-	-	-	1.17E-94	3.06E-250	-	-	-	-	-				
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.39E-51	-	-	-	-	-				
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
Water use	PPO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.19E-01	2.96E-01	3.23E-01	-	-				
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.46E-01	1.59E-01	-	-				
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.19E-01	-	-				
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
Single score	PPO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.45E-01	3.53E-04	3.96E-07			
	LPO - Reference scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.86E-03	3.04E-04			
	LPO - Realistic scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.78E-01			
	LPO - Best scenario	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Mean		3.99E+00	5.58E+00	3.88E+00	1.97E+00	7.80E+01	9.16E+01	5.19E+01	2.68E+01	5.21E+00	1.18E+01	-1.98E+00	-7.68E-03	5.53E-04	5.66E-04	3.49E-04	2.88E-04

Legend: Petroleum-based polyol (PPO), Lignin-based polyols (LPO)
 p-value > 0.05 Indicates a statistical evidence of equality between the true means, i.e., the two systems have the same environmental impact.
 p-value ≤ 0.05 Indicates a statistical evidence of non-equality between the true means, i.e., the two systems do not have the same environmental impact.

into the means presented in Table 8 it is possible to conclude that the best-performing LPO scenario has a lower impact on CC than PPO even when uncertainty is considered. These results suggest that changing from PPO to the best-performing LPO scenario is an effective strategy for reducing the impact on CC as the two systems exhibited significantly different stochastic characterized results for this impact category, with the best-performing LPO scenario having the lowest mean in the Monte Carlo simulation (1.97 kg CO₂ eq.).

PPO was found to have significantly different impact results compared to all three LPO scenarios for RU_f (Table 8). In this case, a comparison between the means of the systems' stochastic results was performed to identify the more environmentally favorable system. The data in Table 8 indicates that the baseline LPO scenario has a higher impact on RU_f than PPO even when uncertainty is factored in. This result is consistent with the conclusion from the deterministic LCA shown in Fig. 8. Moreover, looking into the means presented in Table 8, it is possible to conclude that both the realistic and best-performing LPO scenarios demonstrate a lower impact on fossil resource use than PPO,

even when uncertainty is considered. These findings suggest that transitioning from PPO to either the realistic or best-performing LPO scenarios would be an effective strategy for reducing RU_f, as the systems showed significantly different stochastic characterized results for this impact category. Additionally, the Monte Carlo simulation reveals that both the realistic LPO scenario (5.19 × 10⁻² MJ) and the best-performing LPO scenario (2.68 × 10¹ MJ) have lower mean in the RU_f results compared to PPO (7.80 × 10¹ MJ), highlighting the environmental advantages of these LPO alternatives.

Conversely, PPO was found to have statistically equivalent impact results to all three LPO scenarios for WU (Table 8). This outcome may be attributed to the fact that several LCI results contribute to this impact category, meaning the uncertainty in the inventory data significantly affects WU). Furthermore, the characterization and normalization factors of WU are considered to have high and medium uncertainty, respectively (as detailed in Tables S6 and S7 in the Supplementary Information file). These findings suggest that switching from PPO to any of the LPO scenarios may not be an effective strategy for reducing WU, as

all four systems exhibited significantly equal stochastic characterized results for this impact category.

According to Table 8, PPO was found to have a significantly equal single score to the baseline LPO scenario. However, PPO exhibited a different single score compared to the realistic and best-performing LPO scenarios (Table 8). To determine which system is more environmentally favorable, a comparison of the mean stochastic single scores was performed. The means presented in Table 8 reveal that both the realistic and best-performing LPO scenarios have a lower single score than PPO, even when uncertainty is considered. This conclusion aligns with the findings of the deterministic LCA (Fig. 10). Specifically, the realistic LPO scenario ($3.49 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{Pt}$) and the best-performing LPO scenario ($2.88 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{Pt}$) both have lower mean single scores in the Monte Carlo simulation than PPO ($5.53 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{Pt}$). These results suggest that switching from PPO to the realistic or best-performing LPO scenarios is an effective strategy for reducing overall environmental impact, as both systems demonstrated significantly different and lower stochastic single scores compared to PPO.

3.6. Discussion and limitations

As observed in Fig. 2, the single score indicates that LPO and PPO have similar overall environmental impacts, with values of 556.9 μPt for LPO and 591.3 μPt for PPO. The results presented in the uncertainty analysis confirmed that there is no statistical difference between the single score of the LPO and PPO (Table 8). This means that, from an environmental perspective, using LPO or PPO for coating production (in the reference scenario) will result in the same overall impact.

If practitioners are seeking more environmentally friendly solutions, they should target the realistic or best-case scenarios, where LPO has a lower environmental impact than PPO. In the realistic scenario, the solvent THF is replaced with bio-based THF, which appears to be a greener alternative. While bio-based solvents are gradually being accepted in chemical processes, fully replacing petroleum-based options will still require a lengthy transition due to the need to balance sustainability with economic viability. Choosing bio-based solvents involves verifying their authenticity as sustainable alternatives. Presently, many industries continue to prioritize cost-efficiency over environmental benefits, often overlooking the potential economic impacts associated with long-term environmental damage, which could ultimately counterbalance short-term savings (Li et al., 2019). Thus, the focused development of bio-based solvents tailored to specific applications, including thorough LCAs, should be a top priority. Regarding LPO production, the implementation of bio-based THF at the industrial level appears feasible, particularly given the relatively small price gap between bio-based and petroleum-based THF. Current estimates suggest that bio-based THF can be produced at costs ranging from \$2500 to \$4000 per ton, while petroleum-based THF typically falls between \$3500 and \$4000 per ton (Biomass Magazine, 2022; Zhu et al., 2022). This narrow price differential indicates that industries could transition to bio-based alternatives without significant financial strain. Furthermore, as production technologies advance and economies of scale are achieved, the cost competitiveness of bio-based THF is likely to improve, making its adoption increasingly attractive for companies striving for sustainability (Baker et al., 2023). In the best scenario, in addition to switching to bio-based THF, a renewable energy mix is used. Since the energy mix depends heavily on the country's infrastructure, companies might need to invest in their own renewable energy sources, which could be more expensive and riskier, making this scenario harder to achieve. However, according to the International Renewable Energy Agency (2019), renewable energy deployment needs to accelerate at least six times faster to meet global decarbonization targets aligned with the Paris Agreement. Many companies are actively investing in on-site renewable energy generation, which includes the installation of solar panels and wind turbines. For example, in 2022, corporations globally committed to purchasing a record 36.7 gigawatts (GW) of clean power,

reflecting an 18 % increase from the previous year (BloombergNEF., 2023). The trend indicates a growing recognition among corporations of the importance of integrating renewable energy into their operations, both to mitigate risks associated with energy price volatility and to meet sustainability goals. Regarding LPO production, the implementation of renewable energy production at the industrial level is increasingly feasible. The notable growth in corporate investments in renewable energy demonstrates a clear trend toward integrating sustainable practices within operations. Nevertheless, interestingly, Table 8 shows that there is no statistical difference between the single score of the realistic scenario and best scenarios, meaning that in overall terms, the environmental impact of both scenarios is the same. This insight is valuable for practitioners, as it suggests that while switching to bio-based THF is worthwhile, investing in green energy will not significantly reduce the overall environmental impact (Table 8).

In terms of CC, LPO is found to have a greater negative impact than PPO as indicated in Fig. 7. This conclusion is reinforced by the uncertainty analysis, which reveals a statistical difference between the CC results for LPO and PPO (Table 8). This means that if a company aims to target carbon-neutral solutions or to reduce its carbon footprint, LPO will only be a viable solution if realistic and best scenarios are considered in LPO production. In the realistic scenario, where bio-based THF is used, the carbon footprint of LPO becomes lower than that of PPO. This makes LPO a better option for structures focused on decarbonization, even though this is not true in the reference scenario. For industries seeking the lowest possible contribution to CC, achieving the best scenario, which combines bio-based THF with a renewable energy mix, would be the ideal approach. This scenario further reduces LPO's carbon footprint, and the uncertainty analysis shows a statistically significant difference between the realistic and best scenarios, with the latter having a lower impact on CC. Therefore, for companies targeting the most effective decarbonization strategy, the best scenario should be prioritized. However, it's worth noting that even achieving just the realistic scenario already reduces the carbon footprint below that of PPO, offering a better solution for CC impact reduction.

Regarding the RU_f , LPO performs worse than PPO, as illustrated in Fig. 8. Similarly, from the uncertainty analysis, it was concluded that it exists a statistical difference between LPO and PPO in this category, with LPO having a greater impact (Table 8). To improve LPO's performance in terms of RU_f , at least the realistic scenario must be implemented. In this scenario, switching to bio-based THF already enables LPO to surpass PPO, making it the more environmentally favorable option for reducing fossil resource use. However, as with CC, the best scenario—which combines bio-based THF with a renewable energy mix—yields the lowest RU_f impact. Although the best scenario represents the most environmentally sustainable option, the realistic scenario alone still provides enough improvement to make LPO a better alternative to PPO in terms of RU_f . Therefore, companies can achieve significant reductions in RU_f by simply adopting the realistic scenario, with further benefits if they aim for the best scenario.

When it comes to WU, the results are highly uncertain, making it difficult to determine whether LPO or PPO is the better option in this category. The uncertainty analysis shows no statistically significant difference between the WU impacts of LPO and PPO, even when LPO production is improved under the realistic or best scenarios (Table 8). This suggests that switching from PPO to LPO, regardless of the production scenario, will not result in meaningful changes in WU impacts. For practitioners specifically aiming to reduce WU, neither the realistic nor best scenarios offer a viable solution. Therefore, further research is needed to identify specific areas (or “hotspots”) within the production processes that contribute to WU. This could help in developing more targeted strategies for reducing water use, allowing for more effective environmental improvements in this impact category.

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, it is important to note that many of the process steps involved in LPO production were conducted at a laboratory or pilot scale, with the

corresponding data reflecting a medium technology readiness level (TRL). As an example, the kraft lignin inventory was based on industrial-scale data from another study, while the fractionation of lignin was performed at a laboratory scale, which may not fully represent industrial conditions. This introduces a certain degree of uncertainty to the study's findings. Nevertheless, the uncertainty analysis performed allowed us to assess the confidence levels of the various results. Another limitation is the absence of an economic analysis of the improvements proposed in the realistic and best scenarios. A cost-benefit analysis would be critical to determine the economic feasibility of these environmentally favorable alternatives. Finally, this study lacks a social assessment of the proposed system, which would be essential for a comprehensive sustainability evaluation that encompasses economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Addressing these aspects in future research would provide a more holistic view of the sustainability of LPO production.

4. Conclusions

This work focused on assessing the environmental performance of LPO production. The primary objectives were to identify the most significant contributors to the environmental impacts of the LPO production process, suggest alternatives to mitigate these impacts, and compare LPO with the fossil-based alternatives currently available in the market.

Key finding indicated that CC, RU_f , and WU were found to be the main contributors to the overall environmental impact of LPO production. Two inputs—THF and the electricity mix—were identified as the highest contributors across these categories.

To address these impacts, alternative solutions were proposed. These included the use of bio-based THF derived from butane-1,4-diol made from sugarcane, and the adoption of a renewable energy mix. Implementing these alternatives in different scenarios (realistic and best-performing) showed substantial potential for reducing the environmental footprint of LPO production, ultimately lowering impacts below those of PPO, which can be extremely useful information for practitioners. Moreover, for practitioners, this assessment reveals that LPO generally has a greater impact than PPO in CC and RU_f impact categories, though its performance improves significantly in scenarios that incorporate bio-based THF, especially when combined with renewable energy. In carbon footprint terms, the realistic scenario (using bio-based THF) already makes LPO more favorable than PPO, with even greater benefits in the best scenario (adding renewable energy). However, for fossil resource reduction, both realistic and best scenarios improve LPO's performance, positioning it as an environmentally preferable choice over PPO. For WU, however, no statistically significant difference exists between LPO and PPO, suggesting limited impact change from switching and highlighting the need for targeted research to address WU “hot-spots” in production. This underscores the fact that merely using a natural feedstock like lignin does not automatically guarantee environmental benefits; optimal production parameters must also be met to ensure sustainability. These findings are crucial for guiding the upscaling and industrial demonstration of LPO production.

An uncertainty analysis, conducted via Monte Carlo simulation, further validated these conclusions. Statistical hypothesis tests comparing the stochastic results for PPO and LPO scenarios revealed that shifting from PPO to the best-performing LPO scenario would likely reduce environmental impacts related to CC and RU_f . Moreover, both the realistic and best-performing LPO scenarios demonstrated lower overall environmental impacts compared to PPO. Therefore, from an environmental standpoint, the realistic and best-performing LPO alternatives are more sustainable choices than PPO.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Léo Staccioli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Andreia Maria Rodrigues dos Santos:** Writing – review &

editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **José Gallego:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ana Kalliola:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Olesya Fearon:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Pablo Ortiz:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Walter Pitacco:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Ana Carvalho:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.11.019>.

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